

Grain yield of rice under varietal mixtures and economics. Kerala, India.

Fertilizer schedule (% of recommended dose) ^a		Grain yield (t/ha)			Economics			
WS	DS	WS	DS	Annual	Total income (\$/ha)	Total cost (\$/ha)	Profit (\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
<i>For varietal mixtures</i>								
100	100	2.4	2.5	4.9	726	497	229	1.46
100	75	2.2	2.5	4.7	703	494	209	1.42
100	50	2.3	2.5	4.8	716	489	227	1.46
100	25	2.4	2.3	4.7	712	485	227	1.47
75	100	2.4	2.5	4.9	733	494	239	1.48
75	75	2.3	2.6	4.9	728	491	237	1.48
75	50	2.1	2.2	4.3	657	486	171	1.35
75	25	2.3	2.1	4.4	679	482	197	1.41
50	100	2.3	2.5	4.8	715	489	226	1.46
50	75	2.3	2.6	4.9	728	486	242	1.50
50	50	2.3	2.2	4.5	678	482	196	1.41
50	25	2.2	2.2	4.4	679	478	201	1.42
<i>For single variety</i>								
100	100	2.9	2.7	5.6	747	636	111	1.17
LSD (0.05)		ns ^b	0.3	0.4			-	-

^aRecommended fertilizer schedule was 40-20-20 kg NPK/ha. ^b = not significant.

quantities of crop residue leftover from the WS crop under high N levels.

With regard to annual yield, the 50% WS: 75% DS treatment yielded about the

same as the treatments receiving 100% or 75% in either season. A net savings of 30-15-15 kg NPK/ha occurred, which is 75% of the dose for a single season, by

Residual effects of P on wheat in a rice - wheat sequence

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We assessed the residual effects of fertilizer P sources applied to rice on subsequent wheat growth. The soil was a loamy sand with pH 5.1. 0.59% organic C, 90.96 mg available N/kg (extracted in 0.32% KMnO₄), 3.39 mg available P/kg (Bray I), and 20.45 mg available K/kg (extracted in neutral 1 N NH₄OA₂).

Residual effects of different sources and levels of P applied to rice on subsequent wheat growth.

Treatment	P uptake (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Absolute agronomic efficiency ^a
Control (0 kg P/ha)	3.03	0.8	1.9	-
<i>Sources</i>				
SSP	4.25	0.96	1.99	-
DAP	4.22	0.98	2.00	-
MRP	6.02	1.05	2.02	-
PRP	5.74	1.04	2.01	-
LSD (0.05)	0.75	0.02	0.03	-
<i>P level (kg/ha)</i>				
13.1	4.41	0.96	1.94	10.69
26.2	5.09	1.01	2.00	7.25
39.3	5.68	1.05	2.08	5.95
17.5 kg P applied to wheat	11.97	1.46	2.4	36.57
LSD (0.05)	0.85	0.02	0.04	

^aIncrease in grain yield over control/kg P applied.

cropping varietal mixtures when compared with monocropping.

Cultivating a single variety recorded a narrow increase in annual gross income over varietal mixtures (see table). This was not, however, commensurate with the larger increase in production costs for cultivating single varieties. Savings in cultivation costs of \$139-158 were obtained with varietal mixtures compared with single cultivation.

The system may bring down production costs substantially because the DS crop requires no expenditure for field preparation and transplanting. The reduced production cost contributes to a significantly higher net income and benefit-cost (B-C) ratio with varietal mixtures over a single-cropped variety.

Among the fertilizer levels for the varietal mixture, the 50:75 schedule recorded the maximum net income and B-C ratio. This treatment increased the net income to \$13 over the 100:100 schedule varietal mixture and \$131 over the single variety. ■

We applied 13.1, 26.2, and 39.3 kg P/ha to the rice as either single super-phosphate (SSP) or diammonium phosphate (DAP) at transplanting, or mussorie rock phosphate (MRP) or purulia rock phosphate (PRP) 15 d before transplanting; we also applied 175 kg P/ha as SSP to the wheat at sowing. Both rice and wheat also received 40 kg N/ha and 16.6 kg K/ha. Treatments were replicated three times in a randomized block design. Rice variety Culture 1 and wheat variety Sonalika were used. Wheat was sown at 120 kg seed/ha at a planting depth of 5 cm in rows 20 cm apart.

Significant differences were observed among both sources and levels of P in their residual effects on P uptake and to a lesser extent on grain yield (see table). Differences among sources were greater than those among levels, with the rock phosphates having the greatest residual effect. In no case did the residual effects match the benefit of directly applying P to the wheat. ■